

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL STIFFENED PLATESwaminarayan Patil.^{*1}

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Wagholi, Pune.swamipatil0306@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

In this review paper, the structural & thermal health monitoring of composite material stiffened composite plate by using strain data from Abaqus & Ansys Software Analysis. A numerical analysis and Analytical result of a plate is carried out from the point of view. The numerical analysis and analytical results include the modal analysis, thermal analysis etc., on normal as well as damaged (failure) stiffened composite plate structure. The results of numerical analysis have been compared with software analysis results. It is observed that there is a slight change in the natural frequency of the healthy and damaged structure.

KEYWORDS:

Composite Material, Stiffened Composite Plate, Structural and Thermal Health Monitoring.

INTRODUCTION

Structural health monitoring (SHM) is avoid unexpected failure, for that the process of detecting, locating, and quantifying damage in the structures at before failure. Most SHM methods are a “healthy or normal” condition from that based on the identification of deviations. As before stage of failure the deviations determined the damage where is initiated and some of the method is used to correction of the damage before failure of the structure. In mobile application areas such as marine, aerospace, etc implementation of lightweight structures is therefore a top trend [1]. In composites material the prediction of damage is much more difficult because of the material on which different types of loads is subjected, the material properties are various in different direction as different that composite are orthotropic or may be anisotropic material. Due to this the safety the composite structure reduces as the difficult to predict the damage in the composite structure. In aviation industries requires accurate damage assessment before get in the operation. [2]. A single unattended minor flaw or defect may lead to fatal catastrophic consequences and incur substantial financial losses. [3]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gupta et al.[3]2005 have studied to detect skin-stiffener separation by a neural network based approach. The top skin and the spars are joined and bottom skin of composite test box is made-up. The top skin and the stiffener debonding by removing number of bolts simulate. For different damage cases, static tests are conducted and are compared with normal case. The experimental results explanation with finite element (FE) model is developed for the test box. A neural network is developed and different feedforward backpropagation training algorithms are used for training. Testing of network is prepared by applying experimental records to the network. The performance of the network with different training algorithm is compared in terms of prediction of debond size and its location.

Czigany et al.[4] 2017 have presented multifunctional composite materials, the structural materials in which the sensing properties added as two examples. In one method the glass fiber property such as light transmission was used. Light transmission property change when the fiber is brake or under tension. Another method in which carbon fiber property as electrical conductivity changes according to the load. From the fibers during loading either transmitted electrical voltage signals or light power were continuous monitored and indication by crosshead travel is the deformation value compared. As sensing fiber is broken signal suddenly change.

Seth S. Kessler, [5] in this paper composite structure, Structural Health Monitoring system has been investigated by the frequency response as potential role. For understanding various types of damage effects, a FE model

design and numerical data explored on the normal modes of test and by using impedance meter and scanning laser vibrometer performed experimental results and compared with these results. For low frequencies, the model and experimental results was found good correlation between them.

METHODOLOGY, DESIGN AND MODELLING

The model of the stiffened composite plate was created in ABAQUS CAE. Then the static analysis of the stiffened composite plate has been carried out to determine the stresses and displacements at various locations in the structure. It was followed by the modal analysis of the structure for determining the natural frequencies and its mode shapes. Fig.1 shows the 3D representation of the Stiffened Composite Plate Structure.

Fig.1 3D representation of Stiffened Plate

In the modal analysis was performed and the numerical analysis results were validated with the analytical results for the natural frequencies of the individual plate, stiffener and then the assembled component.

Fig.2 Displacement contour plot for first mode frequency of the plate and stiffener

Fig.3 Displacement contour plot for first mode frequency of the Stiffened Plate Structure and Deformation contour plot for the stiffened composite plate structure

The modal analysis was carried out for the first 4 natural frequencies and their corresponding mode shapes.

Table.1 First 4 natural frequencies for stiffened plate

Mode No	Frequency (Cycles/Time)Hz
1	7.13
2	17.93
3	54.99
4	117.03

RESULT DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The natural frequency of the plate is obtained as 4.75 Hz and 4.80 Hz, the natural frequency of the stiffener is obtained as 51.82 Hz and 54.28 Hz for the fix–free boundary condition from the theoretical and numerical study respectively. The natural frequency of the Stiffened Plate Structure is obtained as 7.17 Hz from theoretical calculations and 7.13 Hz from numerical analysis. The numerical analysis results are close to the analytical results from the various iterations conducted.

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